

Chloralides from α -Hydroxycarboxylic Acids and their Reduction Products.

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Numerous investigators (Städeler, *Annalen*, 1847, 61, 101; 1858, 106, 254 ; Wallach, *ibid.*, 1878, 193, 1; Otto, *ibid.*, 1888, 239, 262 ; Kekule, *ibid.*, 1858, 105, 293 ; Grabousky, *Ber.*, 1873, 6, 255, 1070 ; 1875, 8, 1433 ; Schiff, *ibid.*, 1898, 31, 1898 ; Edeleanu and Zacharia, *Chem. Zentr.*, 1895, II, 212 ; Patterson and Macmillan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1912, 101, 794 ; Böeseken, *Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1926, 35, 1084) have studied the chloralides derived from α -hydroxycarboxylic acids. A solitary instance of reduction of a chloralide by zinc and hydrochloric acid is recorded (Wallach, *loc. cit.*).

In a previous paper (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 11, 467) the authors showed that a certain chloralide is reduced with production of a mixed ether in which one of the radicals is derived from the alcohol $\text{HO}\cdot\text{CH}_2\cdot\text{CHCl}_2$. Because such ethers are hardly known, the authors have prepared the chloralides of malic, tartaric, citric, mandelic and benzilic acids and have reduced them.

Wallach (*loc. cit.*) prepared chloralides by heating the components in sealed tubes and obtained poor yields. The authors have prepared some of them by the method employed by Bhatt (*J. Univ. Bombay*, 1932, 1, 222) which consists in mixing the acid, chloral hydrate and sulphuric acid. This method, however, proved unsatisfactory with aromatic acids and Wallach's method had to be used.

Benzilic acid chloralide has been obtained for the first time. Some of the other chloralides prepared have different melting points from those recorded by previous investigators (Wallach, *loc. cit.* Bhatt, *loc. cit.* Böeseken, *Proc. K. Akad. Wetensch. Amsterdam*, 1927, 30, 55 ; Yorston, *Rec. trav. chim.*, 1927, 46, 711). This

difference is due either to the variety of the acid used (racemic or active) or to the method of preparation. The following table shows the melting points of various chloralides recorded by various workers.

Chloralide of	Wallach.	Bhatt.	Böesecken.	Yorston.	Shah and Alimchandani.
Malic acid	139-40°	139-40°	—	—	180-181°
Tartaric acid	122-24°	128-30°	116-18°	160°	161-62°
	—	156-58°	159-61°	173°	175°
Citric acid	—	161-62°	166°	—	164°
Mandelic acid	82-83°	82-83°	—	—	71°

Previous workers have used *l*-malic acid, whilst the acid used by the authors was optically inactive. Wallach's tartaric acid chloralide differs from that of later workers, because though he started like them with a *d*-tartaric acid, the product obtained by him was inactive owing to racemisation when the acid and chloral were heated together at 150-60° (*cf.* Bhatt, *loc. cit.*). From *d*-tartaric acid, Böesecken obtained two chloralides and Yorston (*loc. cit.*) also got two products. The authors first got Böesecken's product (m.p. 116-18°), which on further crystallisations gave two products (m.p. 161-62° and 175°), which agree with the products of Yorston and as suggested by him, are *cis-trans* isomers. Our citric acid chloralide corresponds with that of previous workers. The mandelic acid that we used was the inactive variety (m.p. 118-19°); and on condensation with chloral, it gives a chloralide (m.p. 71°). In spite of repeated crystallisations, we could not get the higher melting point.*

These chloralides on treatment with alkalis decompose giving chloroform, except benzilic acid chloralide which is remarkably stable.

The chloralides have been reduced using zinc dust and acetic acid, the reduction proceeding in a similar manner to that of the group $\text{CH}(\text{OH})\text{CCl}_3$ (Meldrum and co-workers, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1925,

* The chloralides

being saturated ring compounds admit of *cis-trans* isomerism; the radicals CCl_3 and R may be situated on the same side of the ring or on opposite sides. The work on this isomerism is in progress and shall form a future communication. A preliminary note on this isomerism was read in the Chemistry Section of the Indian Science Congress, Bombay, 1934.

2, 1; 1932, 9, 483; Shah and Alimchandani, *ibid.*, 1931, 8, 262).

The chloralide ring

is reduced to the group $\begin{array}{c} | \\ -\text{C}-\text{O}-\text{CH}_2\text{CHCl}_2 \\ | \\ \text{COOH} \end{array}$ in five instances

including the one in the preceding paper. Citric acid chloralide is exceptional in that its reduction product contains the group

Both the chloralides of tartaric acid on reduction give identical products.

Saturated formula have been assigned to the reduction products described here because they did not absorb bromine in chloroform or ethereal solution.

These reduction products are stable towards dilute alkalis and can be easily titrated; on heating with sulphuric acid, hydrochloric acid gas is evolved and the substance decomposes.

EXPERIMENTAL

Malic acid chloralide.—Inactive malic acid (Kahlbaum, m. p. 130°, 7 g.) and chloral hydrate (8 g.) were shaken with concentrated sulphuric acid (20 c. c.), when a clear solution was formed which solidified after an hour. The mixture was kept overnight and filtered using flannel and the solid washed and dried. It was crystallised from acetic acid and water and finally from hot chloroform as glistening plates, m. p. 180-81°, yield 7.5 g. (Found: Cl, 40.15. $\text{C}_6\text{H}_5\text{O}_5\text{Cl}_3$ requires Cl, 40.39 per cent).

Reduction of the malic acid chloralide.—To the suspension of the chloralide (5 g.) in glacial acetic acid (35 c. c.) zinc dust (10-12 g.) was gradually added and after each addition the mixture was shaken. The mixture was shaken for about an hour, when the chloralide dissolved. The filtered solution was neutralised with sodium carbonate and

the calcium salt, prepared by adding calcium chloride to the boiling solution, was decomposed with dilute sulphuric acid, the calcium sulphate removed and the filtrate extracted with ether, dried with sodium sulphate and the ether removed and the solid obtained was crystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum benzine as rectangular plates, m. p. 130-31°, yield 2 g. (Found: Cl, 30·5; Equiv., 114·9. $C_6H_8O_5Cl_2$ requires Cl, 30·70 per cent. Equiv., 115·5).

Tartaric acid chloralide.—*d*-Tartaric acid (15 g.) and chloral hydrate (33 g.) were shaken with sulphuric acid (50 c.c.) and solid was collected after $\frac{1}{2}$ hour and washed with water. It was crystallised from dilute acetic acid and further purified by dissolving in ether and adding petroleum benzine; prismatic needles, m. p. 161-62°, yield 10 g. On adding more petroleum benzine to the warm mother liquor thin rectangular plates were obtained which were recrystallised from the same solvent as long thin needles, m. p. 170°, yield 4 g. (Found: Cl, 51·75. $C_8H_4O_6Cl_6$ requires Cl, 52·0 per cent).

Reduction of tartaric acid chloralides.—Both the chloralides were separately reduced under similar conditions. Each chloralide (5 g.) was dissolved in acetic acid (25 c.c.) and zinc dust (10 g.) added as described above. The acetic acid filtrate was nearly neutralised with Na_2CO_3 and evaporated to half the bulk, which on acidification with hydrochloric acid gave the reduction product. It crystallised from boiling water as thin light lustrous plates, m. p. 216-17° (decomp.). (Found: Cl, 39·36; Equiv., 182, 180. $C_8H_{10}O_6Cl_4, H_2O$ requires Cl, 39·17 per cent. Equiv., 181). The molecule of water could not be removed even on heating to 170° without decomposition.

Citric acid chloralide.—Citric acid (11 g.), chloral hydrate (8 g.) and sulphuric acid (20 c.c.) were mixed, the materials on shaking for about an hour formed a clear solution. After 24 hours, it was poured over ice. The solid was collected, washed with cold water and crystallised from a mixture of glacial acetic acid and concentrated hydrochloric acid, m. p. 164°.

Reduction of citric acid chloralide.—To the hot solution of chloralide (50 g.) in glacial acetic acid (125 c.c.) zinc dust was added as described before. Vigorous reaction took place and the mixture boiled gently. The product was obtained by preparing

the barium salt, which after removing barium as sulphate gave needle shaped crystals on concentration to a small bulk, which were recrystallised from a mixture of ether and petroleum ether as rhombic crystals, m. p. 208° . It crystallised from concentrated hydrochloric acid in clusters of needles. (Found: Cl, 24.84; Equiv., 143.8. $C_8H_8O_7Cl_2$ requires Cl, 24.71 per cent, Equiv., 143.5).

Mandelic acid chloralide.—Inactive mandelic acid (10 g.) and freshly distilled chloral (16 g.) were heated in a sealed tube at $120-25^{\circ}$ for about 3 hours. On cooling, the contents were poured into water, a white thick paste separated, which was repeatedly washed with water, when it solidified on keeping. It was first crystallised from dilute acetic acid from petroleum benzine and finally from absolute alcohol as prismatic crystals, m. p. $70-71^{\circ}$. (Found: Cl, 37.83. $C_{10}H_7O_3Cl_3$ requires Cl, 37.82 per cent).

Reduction of mandelic acid chloralide.—The chloralide (6 g.) dissolved in acetic acid (20 c.c.) was reduced as before. The product was precipitated as zinc salt, which on acidification with concentrated hydrochloric acid gave an oil which slowly solidified. It crystallised from benzene as rhombic plates, m. p. $114-15^{\circ}$, yield 3 g. (Found: Cl, 28.56; Equiv., 248.6. $C_{10}H_{10}O_3Cl_2$ requires Cl, 28.47 per cent. Equiv., 248.9).

Benzilic acid chloralide.—Benzilic acid (5 g.) and freshly distilled chloral (8 g.) were heated in a sealed tube for about 5 hours at $160-65^{\circ}$. The contents were poured into water and the oil separating was washed with water when it solidified slowly. It was crystallised from glacial acetic acid and then from absolute alcohol as prismatic needles, m. p. 70° . (Found: Cl, 29.97. $C_{16}H_{11}O_3Cl_3$ requires Cl, 29.77 per cent).

The same chloralide was prepared also by heating the acid and chloral in a flask over a small flame and keeping the molten mixture in contact with concentrated hydrochloric acid in a bottle for 24 hours. This chloralide is remarkably stable towards alkaline solutions.

Reduction of benzilic acid chloralide.—To the solution of the chloralide (9 g.) in glacial acetic acid (45 c.c.) zinc dust (15 g.) was added as before. After some time, the mixture solidified; more acid was added and the unchanged zinc removed. The filtrate was neutralised with sodium carbonate and diluted with water when a pasty mass separated; it was washed with water, when it solidified. On crystallising from benzene, a small quantity of a crystalline

product was obtained, m. p. 102-4°. (Found: Cl, 21.61. $C_{16}H_{14}O_3Cl_2$ requires Cl, 21.82 per cent).

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